

Quarantine Regulations in Lev 13: Social Isolation Out of Anxiety and Helplessness, as Well as Hope and Faith

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“Quarantine” almost always means the absolute separation – either limited as to a given time or even lifelong – of a person or a group of people apart from the society because of special hygiene reasons. Mostly it is an act of a society’s self-protection against highly contagious virus diseases which may easily lead to epidemics or even pandemics. The modern term is of French origin and does literally mean “a forty-days timespan”, since in the late middle ages – when the term came in use – people thought 40 days to be the ideal timespan for healing and fully recovering. This believing in a somehow supernatural power of a 40 days span, of course, was of strongly biblical and other ancient scriptural influence. Even if the technical term reaches back only to the middle ages, the described phenomenon is much older and can also be shown in ancient near eastern cultures and in even earlier ones as well.

The Biblical Text

Within the Old Testament we find the most far extended quarantine regulations in Leviticus 13, especially verses 1-8; 45-46. The text is embedded into a series of various cases leading to (cultic and/or hygienic) impurity caused by natural or accidental physical diseases, and presents itself as testcase documenting the deep-rooted

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interdependency of natural science, medicine and theology. Virus diseases were often found to being seen as God’s punishment or at least as departing from the physical body as a result of priestly or even magic rites. Lev 13:1-8; 45-46 runs as follows:

By trusting in the priest’s decision and also in a healing process within a 14-days-isolation under the priest’s auspice, they showed their faith in God.

The LORD spoke to Moses and Aaron, saying: When a person has on the skin of his body a swelling or an eruption or a spot, and it turns into a leprous disease on the skin of his body, he shall be brought to Aaron the priest or to one of his sons the priests. The priest shall examine the disease on the skin of his body, and if the hair in the diseased area has turned white and the disease appears to be deeper than the skin of his body, it is a leprous disease; after the priest has examined him he shall pronounce him ceremonially unclean.

But if the spot is white in the skin of his body, and appears no deeper than the skin, and the hair in it has not turned white, the priest shall confine the diseased person for seven days. The priest shall examine him on the seventh day, and if he sees that the disease is checked and the disease has not spread in the skin, then the priest shall confine him seven days more. The priest shall examine him again on the seventh day, and if the disease has abated and the disease has not spread in the skin, the priest shall pronounce him clean; it is only an eruption; and he shall wash his clothes, and be clean.

But if the eruption spreads in the skin after he has shown himself to the priest for his cleansing, he shall appear again before the priest. The priest shall make an examination, and if the eruption has spread in the skin, the priest shall pronounce him unclean; it is a leprous disease.

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The person who has the leprous disease shall wear torn clothes and let the hair of his head be disheveled; and he shall cover his upper lip and cry out, "Unclean, unclean." He shall remain unclean as long as he has the disease; he is unclean. He shall live alone; his dwelling shall be outside the camp.

The Procedure of Quarantine

This part of the text at first glance seems to deal with skin diseases causing cultic impurity. A more careful reading, however, may shed some light on a handful of exciting details. Firstly, it is important to know, that any long-term impurity for divine cult automatically led to social impurity and therefore exclusion from any human face-to-face contact as well. Secondly, despite the appearance of numerous kinds of skin diseases, the text only differentiates between two cases, namely if it was a leprous disease or not. The reason for that is to be seen in the leprous diseases' being derived from highly contagious virus infections which were as a rule incurable, whereas non leprous skin diseases almost always were curable and not thus contagious as well. Thirdly, the proof of the quality of a disease may pass through up to three steps: if one shows symptoms, he or she is sent to the priest. The priest makes a first check of the disease; is it without any doubt leprous, the person is to be declared unclean, is there a doubt remaining, a quarantine of seven days is to be directed. On the seventh day, the priest makes a second check; is there no

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clear and visible negative change, another seven days of quarantine are directed.

Thereafter, the priest makes a third check; is there still no negative change to state, the person is declared as clean and gets reintegrated into the society, if there is, he or she is declared as unclean and sent in a long-term or even lifelong quarantine. If one stays in a seven-days-quarantine, he or she for this timespan just has to be separated from the society. If one stays in a long-term quarantine, he or she has to settle outside the village, separate oneself from all the others, and fulfilling additional rules; these are above all the covering of one's upper lip and to make sure, that nobody may catch the virus by drawing too near.

Anxiety-Helplessness and Hope-Faith

The reasons for all these regulations at least were the feelings of anxiety about one's own and the whole society's health and welfare on the one and of absolute helplessness considering the dangerousness of a highly contagious virus on the other hand. But at the same time the text also contains information about hope and faith of the ancient Israelites. By keeping all the given rules, they expressed their hope for keeping the virus outside their villages and (bedouin) camps. By trusting in the priest's decision and also in a healing process within a 14-days-isolation under the priest's auspice, they showed their faith in God.

Concluding Remarks

In the moment we face a worldwide virus based pandemic crisis, and we have similar feelings to those of biblical Israel, namely first of all anxiety and helplessness. And we trust in

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similar reactions: we separate cases of suspicion as well as confirmed ones from the society, many cover their upper lip with nose-mouth-masks and we try to keep distance between one another. But we may also take example by the biblical narration according to hope and faith. Good hope many of us do have; we are willing to accept hard restrictions of our civil liberty, because we trust in the ordered regulations. Nevertheless, quite a number of our brothers and sisters suffer intensely; many have already lost beloved fellows, others lost their jobs, the already poor become even poorer, and so on. The bible text encourages us to keep believing in God's grace, mercifulness and love, also – and especially – in a time as we face it currently. Our nowadays priests' duty is not any more to make the medical checks, according to this we trust in our medical doctors, but pastoral care and mission – done by priests, religious and lay spiritual advisors – may be a chance for Christian communities to foster our common Christian faith and to make Christian charity visible. That does not change the situation as such we experience, but it makes our common hope for better times much more realistic and cheerful

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